

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

DARAYEVA SEVARA

THE IMPACT OF ALISHER NAVOI AND ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD BOBUR'S MASTERPIECES ON RENAISSANCE IN XV CENTURY AS WELL AS THEIR ROLE IN SOCIETY.

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